

Quantum Dynamical Probability and the Uncertainty Principle

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The uncertainty principle (linked to p, x or E, t) plays an important role in quantum mechanics. For example, an electron with an exact momentum p is described by a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. This function exists at all x points and so it is suggested in the literature that there is complete uncertainty as to the electron's position. (More specifically $P(x) = \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ normalization constant = constant and so all x points have the same probability.) Thus if p is completely certain, it is said that position x is completely unknown. We note, however, that $\exp(ipx)$ consists of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which are repeated probability distributions (with zero endpoints). Thus even though they exist in all of space, due to repetition which in turn is due to spatial invariance, there is a specific length number, namely the wavelength. Thus we argue that in classical physics there is a set of points (x, p) , but in quantum mechanics (p , x with its dx interval), with the latter being equal to \hbar/p . Then the only uncertainty is within the dx interval i.e. the wavelength and spatial density is linked to momentum i.e. there is dynamical probability. In particular, there is a frequency \hbar/E and a wavelength \hbar/p which define an internal clock and ruler and the two are independent. Thus within a wavelength one has a probabilistic picture (in order to have endpoints defining the dx interval) and no sense of time, yet on average time exists because of \hbar/E and the particle moves in space with a constant v .

This begs the question: How do time and space x arise in such a scenario? We speculate the following. Assume there exists a property called energy which defines an object. This object, however, may break into two different objects. As a result, one introduces a parameter called time to distinguish between the two systems (E) and (E_1, E_2). For a certain time range one has a single object, while for a later time interval, one has two objects. Each of the two objects in the second system, however, needs to be distinguished as well and so another parameter, namely space x is used for this. If the two objects existed at the same x and t , how would one know there were two unless another parameter were introduced? We use t and x as the distinguishing parameters and furthermore give these a measure i.e. dt and dx . We then argue that from these ideas one may show the notion of speed and direction (because there are two objects) as well as conservation of momentum arises. Given the notion of an interval, we argue it must be described by a probability distribution and we link this to \hbar/p and $\exp(ipx)$. We finally note that since spatial density is linked to dynamical probability, one must consider motion associated with a density which may lead even to collective motion.

Notions of Time and Space

The Heisenberg uncertainty principle:

$$\text{Standard deviation}(p) \text{ Standard deviation}(x) \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((1a))$$

$$\text{Standard deviation}(E) \text{ Standard deviation}(t) \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((1b))$$

makes use of x, t, E and p . As a first step, we speculate on how these may arise in nature.

First we define an object by a quantity called energy. At this stage, there is no time t or space x . We then suggest there is nothing to prevent the object from splitting into two objects. A parameter, however, needs to be introduced to distinguish between the two systems (E) and (E_1, E_2) and we call this time t . Furthermore we introduce the measure dt . Thus there is a time interval during which there is one object and a later time interval in which there are two objects. The two objects within the second system, however, must be distinguished and as they exist in time already, we suggest introducing a new parameter space x . We also assume that this is linked to a measure dx . (One might argue that a different parameter may be used, but we consider x here.)

At this point, we have the notion of E energy, x and dx and t and dt , but no momentum. Assume that energy is conserved i.e. that $E = E_1 + E_2$. There is no reason the two objects have a fixed x in t . We assign an $x=0$ to the single object with E and then measure x_1 and x_2 from $x=0$ to the two objects. Assume $E_1 > E_2$ and that $x_1/t = v_1 = \text{constant}_1$ and $x_2/t = v_2 = \text{constant}_2$. In such a case $E_1 v_1$ and $E_2 v_2$ are fluxes so the notion of momentum appears (although formally it is divided by the constant cc). By assuming a balance of flux:

$$E_1 v_1 = E_2 v_2 \quad ((2)) \text{ or momentum conservation}$$

Even though E_1 and E_2 differ, there is energy conservation as well as momentum conservation. Now the notion of E , p , v , x , dx , t and dt exists. Furthermore, given that x is associated with two objects one may have two directions at the same t .

Dx and Probability

We argue in the above section for associating x with an interval dx and t with an interval dt . We now suggest that such an interval must be physically manifested. In other words we suggest it is not a mathematical construct which may necessarily be taken to 0. An interval dx suggests a probability distribution with a 0 value at the endpoints in order to distinguish the region dx . Furthermore it seems to have nothing to do with time i.e. the parameter t and dt . Then what does it depend on?

For constant motion $x/t = v = \text{constant}$, any x point is as good as another, yet somehow there is a distribution in x also present, which almost seems like a contradiction. The distribution in x suggests dx is finite. Furthermore there is the question of direction of motion, so the probability distribution in x should distinguish between forward and backwards motion. This is different from a constant mathematical number dx , dx actually becomes dynamical. It should also distinguish between different p values. A function satisfying all of these requirements is $\exp(ipx)$. It maps to 1 i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ suggesting all x points are the same. It distinguishes between p and $-p$ and also between different p values. It further allows for positive and negative pieces $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ allowing for probability to disappear from one region and appear in another. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ breaks spatial invariance in a very specific momentum dependent way i.e. introduces \hbar/p "dx" units, but at the same time maps into a constant by representing two dimensions which allow it to distinguish the direction of motion.

An important feature of $\exp(ipx)$ is the wavelength \hbar/p . This suggests a completely known length which maps to a specific p . Within this length there is no notion of time and there is a probabilistic situation. On average, however, the particle must move with speed v which is constant. In other words we suggest that:

$$\text{Classical } p, x \rightarrow p, x = p/m t \text{ with } dx = \hbar/p \quad ((3))$$

The only uncertainty in such a scenario is within the wavelength \hbar/p . $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ simply displays translation invariance, rather than uncertainty for the particle to be at any x point.

To see this in an example, consider a particle in a well with infinite potential walls separated by a length L . If, according to the above argument, the particle is associated with a $dx = \hbar/p$ which consists of a positive hump and a negative one, then:

$$2L = \hbar/p \quad ((4))$$

as the lowest p result. In other words, p defines dx which in turn defines the extent or measure of the particle. Thus any spatial density is necessarily linked with momentum. How can this be for a particle in a box which is localized within L ? One needs to consider both p and $-p$. (One may note that the solution $\sin(px)$ for the box with $p = n\pi/L$ and 0 outside the box may be created by a Fourier series using all $\exp(ipx)$ s which are defined in all of space. Nevertheless the form $\sin(px)$ which is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ is important as it defines the correct distribution $W(x)$ which follows from $-\hbar^2/2m d^2W(x)/dx^2 = E_n W(x)$.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics seems to include a spatial ruler with equal sized dx units. The key point, however, seems to be that this unit shrinks to zero which is at odds with the idea above of an \hbar/p width for a given p . In Newtonian mechanics there is a single velocity state $v = dx/dt$ within dx even though the particle accelerates. The idea seems to be that one may make dx as small as one likes so that the correction to v after the particle passes dx is small i.e. $v + dv$ with $v \gg dv$. If a fixed dx length were imposed in Newtonian mechanics and the initial v is close to zero, then dv may be larger than v and so there cannot be a single v state within dx . Thus the idea of acceleration in a fixed dx picture even in Newtonian mechanics would necessitate a mixture of v states within a single dx .

Quantum Bound State Scenario

Consider the case of the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-\hbar^2/2m d^2W_n/dx^2 + V(x)W_n = E_n W_n \quad ((5))$$

$W_n(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is a superposition of constant p states which add and subtract like a probability wave, but on average create a wavelike object (at least in the harmonic oscillator case) with different heights and widths of peaks such that $KE(x)_{\text{classical}} = -\hbar^2/2m d^2W_n/dx^2$

$dW_n/dx / W_n$. E_n is the energy of the n th level and is associated with $\exp(-iE_n t)$. The missing piece is $\exp(i P x)$ where $P=0$ i.e. the center-of-mass momentum is zero. Thus $W^*(x)W_n(x)$ describes the spatial density profile of the bound object (and is more or less within the classical turning points), but an exact E_n applies and this bound object may be sitting with its center of mass at any x because $P=0$ and \hbar/P is the wavelength for the center of mass (i.e. it is anywhere). In real situations, the center of mass is confined to a region and so P would not be 0.

Notion of Invariance

$\exp(ipx)$ representing a free particle removes time and is linked with the particle being at any x with the same probability. It, however, distinguishes between p and $-p$.

The generator which moves from one x point to another is d/dx and $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$. Thus d/dx seems to be associated with an invariance in x space, but includes a sense of motion direction. Thus the spatial density invariance leads to a dynamical probability which is momentum dependent and not spatially invariant, but which creates its own ruler dx values i.e. \hbar/p . In classical mechanics, spatial density would not necessarily be associated with motion/internal motion, although in classical statistical mechanics it is in the case of a potential $V(x)$. Thus in quantum mechanics one must consider the association of a spatial density with motion. If a particle is trapped in a box of length L its density is within this box and there needs to be a minimum p and $-p$ momentum associated with this length. In such a case there is a local momentum density $-idW/dx / W$ which may be multiplied by W^*W , but integrates to zero because overall the bound system does not translate. Collective motion, however, is possible in the case that an overall wavefunction $W(x)$ of a many nucleon nucleus is not rotationally symmetric. In such a case there are preferred portions of space and so there is angular motion. Thus the spatial density in the quantum case is closely linked to momentum and motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that time and space arise as parameters needed to distinguish between an object with energy E breaking into two objects with E_1 and E_2 . We further argue that these parameters are linked with measures dt and dx . Time distinguishes between the two systems E and $(E_1$ with $E_2)$ and space distinguishes within a system i.e. between E_1 and E_2 . (Another parameter in principle could be used.) We consider the case of x separating E_1 and E_2 and take $x=0$ as associated with E . Conservation of energy yields $E=E_1+E_2$ and E_1 and E_2 have an x_1 and x_2 value relative to $x=0$. It is possible that $|x_1/t|$ and $|x_2/t|$ are constants >0 . In such a case we have argued that conservation of energy flux is equivalent to momentum conservation. We also argue that x is associated with a measure dx which implies a probability distribution with zero values at the beginning and end of dx .

Thus there is no time and only a probabilistic description within dx . At the same time, there is an internal clock ticking as E_1 and E_2 are associated with time. x_1/t and x_2/t are constants implying the objects "move" smoothly with each x point having the same probability, yet dx is a distribution which does not treat all x points the same. Furthermore x_1 and x_2 arise in order to

distinguish between E1 and E2 and it is possible that the probability distributions associated with $dx(1)$ and $dx(2)$. In such a case, the distribution of $dx(i)$ may actually distinguish between forwards and backwards motion and even the magnitude of $p=Ev/cc$. A solution which yields all of these features is $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$ to show all x points have the same $P(x)$.

Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamical probability and spatial density is actually based on momentum (which includes motion). Thus in classical mechanics one has (x,p) , but in quantum mechanics $(p, x$ with $dx=h\bar{h}/p$). We argue that the uncertainty exists within dx and do not think in terms of a given p representing an x which may be anywhere (i.e. infinite uncertainty) because $P(x)=\text{constant}$.

In quantum mechanics, it seems one must associate a spatial density with momentum. For example, if a particle is trapped in a box with infinite potential walls L apart, one must consider a minimum wavelength associated with such a length i.e. $2L= h\bar{h}/p$ (which includes p and $-p$) even though these are really p and $-p$. Sometimes collective motion may be implied. If the nucleons of a nucleus form a wavefunction $W(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\mathbf{p}} a(\mathbf{p})\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ such that $W^*(\mathbf{r})W(\mathbf{r})$ is not spatially symmetric this means little in classical mechanics, but in quantum mechanics indicates rotational symmetry is broken and there is collective angular motion.